

Recent Advances in Some Aspects of High Pressure Chemistry*

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I consider it a great pleasure in expressing my sincere thanks to the Secretary of the Indian Chemical Society and to the members of its Council for the great honour done to me by inviting me to deliver the 6th Acharya Jnan Chandra Ghosh Memorial Lecture for 1967 on his 74th birthday anniversary. I feel proud of this unique honour, as it will give me, being one of his very close and oldest students, an opportunity to pay my humble tribute to the memory of his service to the country as a great scientist, an inspiring and lovable teacher, a great patriot, and above all as a great soul.

Before I actually take up the subject matter of my lecture I shall give you a short biographical sketch of Acharya Jnan Chandra Ghosh and say a few words about him as a scientist and as a man.

Born at Purulia in September 4, 1893 he had his early education in the Giridih High School and later in the Presidency College, Calcutta, where he came in close contact with Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray as the Professor of Chemistry, who exerted a profound influence on his future career and character. After having a brilliant academic record he worked in the Calcutta University as a lecturer in Chemistry for a few years and then proceeded to England for advanced studies and worked there in the University of London. He was awarded the D. Sc. degree of the Calcutta University for his work in the field of electro-chemistry. In 1921 Dr. Ghosh returned to India as the Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry, Dacca University, at an age of only 28 years. This was a unique honour done to him by the then Vice-Chancellor, Dacca University, in recognition of his outstanding contribution 'Ghosh's Law of Dilution.'

Dr. Ghosh worked in the Dacca University for nearly 18 years and took an active part in all-round development of the departments, and expanded the activities, both teaching and research, to a considerable extent. During the later part of his stay there he was responsible for opening a number of sections under his Headship, namely, Bio-chemistry, Physiological Chemistry, Agricultural Chemistry and Botany. At the Dacca University he initiated mainly two schools of research-photo-chemistry and catalysis.

* Acharya Jnan Chandra Ghosh Memorial Lecture, 1967 delivered on September 4, 1967.

In 1938 he joined the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, as its Director and held this post till 1947. As a great scientific planner he not only developed the existing departments, but also opened a number of new important departments/sections/laboratories namely, Chemical Engineering, Metallurgy, Fermentation Technology, Pharmacology, Power Engineering, High Pressure Chemistry, Internal Combustion Engine, Aeronautical Engineering, etc.

In 1948 he left Bangalore and successively occupied a number of key positions, like Director-General of Industries, Supplies & Disposals, Govt of India ; Director, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur ; Vice-Chancellor, Calcutta University, and lastly, Member of the Planning Commission, Govt of India. Besides, he was associated with a large number of scientific and other learned associations either as a member or as the Chairman. When he was the Director-General of Industries, Supplies & Disposals, he envisaged the need to start heavy industries in this country for rapid industrialisation and was responsible for planning and setting up a number of oil refineries, fertilizer factories, steel factories, etc. in India. He was also responsible to a considerable extent for the growth and development of the C. S. I. R. laboratories. He will be always remembered for his contributions to the promotion of education, science and technology.

He became the President, Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress held at Banaras in 1925 and General President of the Indian Science Congress, held at Lahore, in 1939. He also served the Indian Chemical Society and the National Institute of Sciences of India as Presidents.

Dr. Ghosh was a man of rare qualities. He had charming manners and was easily approachable by everybody. Due to his outstanding personal qualities he was loved and respected by all those who had come in contact with him. He was a real friend of the poor. When he was at Dacca he used to help regularly a large number of poor students in kind or cash. He was a great patriot, too. He used to help financially some of the political organisations like Khadi Pratisthan, etc. He had a very soft corner for the oppressed and political sufferers.

Dr. Ghosh married Nilima Ghosh (nee Palit) in 1922 and had a very happy married life. His wife identified herself with his activities and is a very kind, affectionate and ideal hostess.

The research activities of Dr. Ghosh covered varied fields of pure and applied chemistry. He made original and outstanding contributions in the fields of electrochemistry, photochemistry, chemical kinetics and catalysis. Some of the highlights of his contributions are given below :

In 1918 Dr. Ghosh propounded his revolutionary theory of electrolytic dissociation of strong electrolytes, known as "Ghosh's Law of Dilution", which evoked world wide interest. The theory received immediate support from famous scientists like Walter Nernst, Max Planck, Sir William Bragg, Prof. G. N. Lewis and others and

paved the way for further developments by Debye and Hückel. Acharya Jnan Chandra will always be remembered for this fundamental contribution. In fact, Dr. Ghosh initiated researches in electrochemistry in India and published a series of papers during the years, 1918-21, and also in later years. Ghosh and co-workers made measurements of electrode potentials of mercury against its ions in aqueous methanol, acetone and pyridine by determining the maximum positions of the electrocapillary curves. The reduction potentials of cysteine - cystin mixtures on mercury surface, the redox potential of glutathione, and that of ascorbic acid, thioglycollic and thiolactic acids were also determined by these workers. In industrial electrochemistry Dr. Ghosh and Dr. S. K. Bhattacharyya successfully prepared glycol, chlorohydrin, chloral, chlorobenzene, and benzoquinone using porous carbon as electrodes with high current efficiencies.

Dr. Ghosh also made important contributions in photochemistry. In collaboration with a large number of brilliant workers he studied the kinetics of photochemical reactions both in homogeneous and heterogeneous phases involving bromination, iodination, oxidation and reduction. Using some inorganic colloids like tungstic acid sol, vanadium pentoxide sol, molybdic acid sol, etc., as photo sensitisers, he studied the kinetics of a number of reactions using dextro - and laevo - circularly polarised light of different frequencies and obtained a wealth of information regarding the fundamental mechanism of such changes. In some cases, he discovered circular dichroism of photo-sensitiser, which assumed anisotropy due to excitation in ultraviolet light. These observations promise great importance in the synthesis of optically active compounds. He also studied some photochemical reactions in thixotropic gels involving oxidation of sugars by dyes using zinc oxide as a sensitiser.

Redox reactions in biological systems also attracted his attention and a number of publications were made by him and his co-workers on this subject. He studied autoxidation of ascorbic acid and its inhibition by sulphur compounds (containing -SH and -S-S- groupings). He also observed that low concentrations of oxidized or reduced glutathione, cysteine, or thiolpropionic acid, inhibit the autoxidation of dissolved NaHSO_3 at pH 7.0 and 20°C . The effect is, however, counteracted by copper or mercury salts.

Dr. Ghosh was a pioneer in this country in his research activities in many respects. He visualised as early as 1924 that the future industry of the country would be either coal based or petroleum based. He was the first to start work on catalytic gaseous reactions of technical importance and studied the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis to produce synthetic oils and paraffins and developed a few catalysts, which promise great industrial importance. He made notable contributions on adsorption of gases on solid catalysts of industrial importance, e.g., ammonia synthesis, Fischer-Tropsch synthesis and methanol synthesis and suggested probable mechanisms of the synthetic processes.

Over and above this intensive research programme in widely varying fields Dr. Ghosh was associated with various Government projects and industrial problems

from time to time and was responsible for the successful guidance of the work of many brilliant young collaborators on technical problems relating to the production from Indian raw materials of phosphatic fertilizers, urea, ammonium sulphate, formaldehyde, synthetic rubber, titanium oxide, phosphorous, carbon disulphide, hydrogen peroxide, potassium chlorate, sodium, magnesium, graphite, synthetic fuels, and few others.

As one of his last outstanding contributions Acharya Jnan Chandra wrote a book entitled "Some catalytic gas reactions of industrial importance" with Dr. S. K. Bhattacharyya and Dr. M. V. C. Sastry as co-authors—a treatise which may be considered as one of the most authoritative and up-to-date of its kind in the world.

He had left behind a legacy, a band of sincere, honest and brilliant students, who are now occupying prominent positions all over the country in the fields of science, technology and administration.

During my stay at Bangalore it was Dr. Ghosh, who created a great interest in me and initiated me to take up Catalysis and High Pressure Chemistry as my future fields of research activities. To express my deep sense of gratitude to that great soul for the guidance and encouragement, which I received from him, I have chosen the subject matter of the memorial lecture today as "Recent Advances in some aspects of High Pressure Chemistry", a subject in which I have been interested for the last twenty years.

To a remarkable extent the interest in high pressure chemistry started from the pioneering work of V. Ipatieff in Russia and F. Haber in Germany, who started the work in and around 1901, and in High Pressure Physics from the work of P. W. Bridgman, who began his work in the Harvard University in 1908.

During the last sixty years some of the most outstanding discoveries and developments in Chemistry and Chemical Technology have been made possible by the use of high pressure. The industrial processes namely, the synthesis of ammonia, urea, methanol, liquid fuels by Fischer-Tropsch and Bergius processes, oxo-synthesis and polyethylenes, etc., have now been established on a more economic and sound footing based on high pressure, producing more than 6 million tons of chemicals per annum.

During the last World War II and immediately after a large number of new and completely novel syntheses of organic compounds were discovered using carbon monoxide, acetylene and other cheap raw materials mainly by two active schools of research in Germany under Walter Reppe and Otto Roelen. The results of their discoveries were mostly patented—the only information, which can be obtained, is supplied by BIOS and FIAT reports, and a few published papers. The vast amount of data obtained by the different workers have led to a new branch of Chemistry known as "Carbon monoxide and Acetylene Chemistry". These results promise great industrial importance and, therefore, considerable research activities have been

concentrated during the last 20 years all over the world to find out the economic feasibility of the various syntheses reported for their industrial exploitation.

More recently the syntheses of diamond and a number of minerals, which occur in nature, have been achieved using ultra high pressures and high temperatures. For the synthesis of diamond, as followed by G. E. C., U.S A., and A.S.E.A., Sweden, the temperature is kept above 2000°K and the pressure applied ranges from 10 to 8.5×10^4 atmospheres. Synthetic diamond has got a number of advantages over the natural diamond. It can be tailored to any size and given any tinge by incorporating traces of impurities. It is harder and chemically more inert than natural diamond. Borazon, boron nitride, is another very important product of high pressure. It is not only harder than diamond but also almost completely unaffected by oxygen even at high temperature and as such, can be very profitably used as drilling head. Though the synthesis of diamond enjoys a glamour for obvious reasons, no less is the importance of the high pressure synthesis of naturally occurring minerals in the laboratory. Many common minerals like feldspars, brucite, pyroxene jadeite, kyanite, albite, anorthite and numerous others have been prepared in the laboratory using ultra high pressure and high temperature. This extension of high pressure research in the areas of geochemistry and geophysics has brought to light a number of valuable facts about the formation of the earth, mechanism of formation of different rocks and minerals.

In the field of high pressure physics spectacular results have recently been reported on changes in the physical properties of elements and compounds when they are subjected to ultra-high pressure, e.g., compressibilities of solids, polymorphic changes, changes in dielectric properties, optical properties, electrical properties, and molecular properties like surface tension, viscosity, refractive index, etc. besides those already known from Bridgman's work.

In the field of high pressure design attempts are being made to build equipments, which can produce and maintain a static pressure upto 4,00,000 atmosphere or more. Two types of ultra high pressure— high temperature apparatus are receiving rather extensive uses at the present time. The 'Belt'¹ utilises conical "pistons" thrust into opposite ends of a properly shaped and gasketed chamber i.e., surrounded by a torroidal "belt" of supporting rings. The second device is the 'Tetrahedral Anvil'² apparatus. This device is geometrically the simplest of a series of related devices, which make use of polygonal anvils that enclose regular polyhedra when fitted together about a common point. Pressure is generated by forcing the anvils against a polyhedral cell of pyrophyllite.

Most of the industrial chemical processes are operated within the pressure range, 50-100 atm. For some laboratory scale of experiments pressures upto 20,000 atm. have been used. For syntheses of diamond and many naturally occurring minerals pressures upto 100,000 atm. are being extensively used.

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It may be interesting to know that the highest static pressure attained in the laboratory, till today, is about 400,000 atm. Even so, our attainment falls miserably below the 'pressure store' provided by nature, which is estimated to be extended upto a maximum of 10^{18} atm. in the centre of white dwarf stars.

With these introductory remarks I shall now devote the rest of my lecture in reviewing the recent advances made by me in high pressure chemistry at the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, and at the Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, in collaboration with a band of brilliant research workers, namely, Dr. S. Sourirajan, Dr. Soumen Sen, Dr. Dharm Vir, Dr. S. K. Palit, Dr. S. N. Nag, Dr. D. K. Nandi, Dr. A. K. Sen, Dr. C. R. Lahiri, Dr. A. R. Das, Dr. D. P. Bhattacharyya, Dr. G. B. Purohit, Dr. N. Tripathy and few others. This review will deal with two aspects of high pressure chemistry, one on the catalytic syntheses of carboxylic acids and esters from carbon monoxide in presence of nickel, cobalt and iron catalysts and other organic compounds not involving carbon monoxide, and the other, on the kinetics and mechanism of a few acid-catalysed liquid phase hydration of unsaturated organic compounds and hydrolysis of lactones.

High Pressure synthesis of carboxylic acids and esters ; Under this head I shall deal with the reactions which involve the syntheses of carboxylic acids and their esters from carbon monoxide and such simple molecules like alcohols, olefins, aldehydes, ethers, acetylene etc. using as catalysts various compositions of transition metals like iron, cobalt and nickel, supported or unsupported, at a pressure ranging from 50-6000 atmospheres and a temperature ranging from 100-350°C. Most of the recent contributions in this field including some articles³⁻²⁶, are those of the speaker and his co-workers.

The reactions to be discussed here are as follows ;

- (i) Syntheses of acetic, propionic and isobutyric acids (and their esters) from carbon monoxide and methanol, ethanol and isopropanol respectively.³⁻⁵
- (ii) Syntheses of propionic acid (and its esters) from ethylene, carbon monoxide and water/alcohols.^{6,7}
- (iii) Syntheses of formic acid (and its esters) from carbon monoxide and water/alcohols.^{8,9}
- (iv) Syntheses of glycollic acid (and its esters) from formaldehyde, carbon monoxide and water/alcohols.^{10,11}

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10. S. K. Bhattacharyya and D. Vir, *Advances in Catalysis*, 1959, IX, 625, (Proc. of the Inter. Cong. on Catalysis, Philadelphia, U. S. A., 1956).
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(v) Synthesis of adipic acid from tetrahydrofuran, carbon monoxide and water¹².

(vi) Synthesis of δ -valerolactone from tetrahydrofuran and carbon monoxide.¹²

(vii) Syntheses of esters and acids from aliphatic ethers and carbon monoxide^{13,14}.

(viii) Synthesis of esters from alkyl iodide, carbon monoxide and alcohols.^{15,16}

(ix) Syntheses of lactic acid (and its esters) from acetaldehyde, carbon monoxide and water/alcohols^{17,18}.

(x) Syntheses of benzoic acid (and its esters) from chlorobenzene, carbon monoxide and water/alcohols.¹⁹

The reactions involving acetylene are : Carboxylation of acetylene : Syntheses of acrylic acid (and its esters) from acetylene, carbon monoxide and water/alcohols²⁰⁻²⁶.

The optimum conditions and the best catalysts for the above syntheses reactions have been recorded in Table III.

Thermodynamics of the reactions : In order to determine the feasibility of the various synthetic reactions described above, equilibrium constants at various temperatures (Table—I) and pressures (Table—II) were calculated from thermal and fugacity/activity data. From these Tables it can be seen that all the reactions studied are thermodynamically highly feasible.

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TABLE I
Equilibrium constants (K_p) at constant pressure (atm.) and at different temperatures (assuming gaseous state)

Reactions	Temperatures, °C					
	25	100	150	200 (a) or 210 (b)	250	300
1. $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} + \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$	3.55×10^{14}		9.8×10^7	1.05×10^6 (b)	1.0×10^5	7.9×10^3
2. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$	1.5×10^{11}			5.1×10^3 (b)		3.7
3. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + \text{CO} +$ $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$	1.1×10^{15}	6.9×10^8		4×10^3 (a) & 2.8×10^3 (b)		1.6
4. $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{O} +$ $\text{CO} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$	1.2×10^{13}	1.8×10^8		1×10^5 (a) 1.9×10^4 (b)		8.1×10^3
5. $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O} + 2\text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ tetrahydrofuran adipic acid	2.5×10^{34}	1.7×10^{13}		3.5×10^7 (a)		3.4×10^3
6. $\text{CH}_3\text{CHO} + \text{CO} +$ $\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{COOH}$	2.3×10^5	2.4×10^{-1}		1×10^{-3} (a)		$7.04 \times 10^{-}$
7. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2$ $=\text{CHCOOH}$	1×10^{28}	4.4×10^{15}	1.5×10^{13}	2.5×10^9 (a)	1.5×10^7	2×10^5
8. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{CH}_3\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2$ $=\text{CHCOOCH}_3$	7.2×10^{25}	2.9×10^{18}	1×10^{15}	2×10^{10} (a)	1.3×10^{10}	1.6×10^8
9. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2$ $=\text{CHCOOC}_2\text{H}_5$	5.3×10^{27}	8.9×10^{19}	2×10^{16}	2.4×10^{11} (a)	1×10^{11}	1.2×10^9
10. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2$ $=\text{CHCOOC}_4\text{H}_9$		1×10^{21}	2.2×10^{16}	3.3×10^{12} (a)	1.7×10^{10}	2×10^8

TABLE II
Equilibrium constant at constant temperature and different pressures (assuming gaseous state)

Reactions	Pressures (atm)		
	100	200	300
1. $\text{CH}_3\text{OH} + \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$	1.3×10^4	1.5×10^4	1.6×10^4 at 300°C
2. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOH}$	6.7	8.0	8.6 at 300°C
3. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} + \text{CO} + \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$	4.4×10^3	4.6×10^3	4.6×10^3 at 230°C (at 250 atm.)
4. $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{O} + \text{CO} \rightarrow \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$	4.9×10^8	5.8×10^8	5.8×10^8 at 273°C 25 atm. 35 atm. 50 atm.
5. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2 = \text{CHCOOH}$	3.5×10^9	4.6×10^9	7.3×10^9 at 200°C
6. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{CH}_3\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2 = \text{CHCOOCH}_3$	2.4×10^{12}	2.6×10^{12}	3.2×10^{12} at 200°C
7. $\text{C}_2\text{H}_2 + \text{CO} + \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_2 = \text{CHCOOC}_2\text{H}_5$	2.3×10^{16}	2.6×10^{16}	2.6×10^{16} at 150°C

Results and discussions of various carboxylation reactions: All the reactions, which have been studied using carbon monoxide as a reactant, have got almost similar characteristics. This outstanding observation suggests that these reactions involve similar mechanism and the role of catalysts must be the same.

Various supported and unsupported nickel, cobalt and iron catalysts, in the form of reduced metals, carbonyls, organic acid salts or as halides, have been used as

catalysts. Kieselguhr, kaolin, pumice and silica gel have been tried as catalyst supports. Detailed investigations on the comparative activity of various catalysts have led to the following conclusions :

(i) Reduced nickel, cobalt and iron, which are very active catalysts for Fischer-Tropsch and oxo-syntheses are practically inactive as catalysts in the carboxylation reaction cobalt carbonyl as such or when mixed with iodine fail to show appreciable activity,

(ii) Iron, cobalt and nickel halides exhibit excellent catalytic activity, supported halides being superior to free halides. The activity of the metals is in the order Ni>Co>Fe and that of the halides in the order, iodide>bromide>chloride. The fatty acid salts of iron, cobalt and nickel also exhibit almost comparable activities to that of corresponding halides in some cases. Among the different fatty acid salts tried as catalysts (naphthenate, formate, acetate, propionate, & butyrate), the acetate shows highest activity. Among these again the activity of the metals follow the order Ni>Co>Fe.

(iii) As a catalyst support, silica gel is superior to kieselguhr, pumice and kaolin.

(iv). The presence of cuprous iodide, magnesia or thoria in the halide catalysts does not give any promoter effect ; in fact the yield decreases. In a few cases a mixed iodide catalyst (Cu, Mn) supported on silica gel has been observed to be quite active.

Influence of process variables :—The influence of process variable such as pressure, temperatures, residence period, molar ratio of the reactants, amount of catalyst for fixed amount of feed and the catalyst-support-ratio have been studied in detail. Experiments were conducted by keeping all the variables, except one, constant. The results obtained with nickel iodide supported on silica gel as the catalyst are shown graphically in the corresponding Figures. The optimum conditions for each synthesis is recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

*Optimum conditions for carboxylic acid and ester synthesis
(the catalysts supported over silica gel)*

Acid or Ester	Catalyst	Pressure, p.s.i.	Optimum Temp. °C	% Conversion to acid or ester
Acetic	NiI ₂ - SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	4000	200	40.0% methanol
	CoI ₂ - SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	4000	220	18.8% ..
Propionic	NiI ₂ - SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	4200	230	37.3% ethanol
	CoI ₂ - SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	4200	230	22.3% ..
Glycollic	NiI ₂ - SiO ₂ (89 : 11)	8600	200	45.0% formaldehyde
	CoI ₂ - SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	8700	215	42.0% ..
	FeI ₂ - SiO ₂ (85 : 15)	8800	230	27.1% ..

Table III (contd.)

Acid or Ester	Catalyst	Pressure, p.s.i.	Optimum Temp. °C	% Conversion to acid or ester
Methyl glycollate	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	5100	180	25.3% Formaldehyde
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	5600	200	20.1% "
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	5600	200	12.2% "
Ethyl glycollate	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (70 : 30)	5600	200	24.0% Formaldehyde
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (69 : 31)	5600	200	20.5% "
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (69 : 31)	5600	200	11.8% "
Adipic	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (78 : 22)	4500	200	23.0% tetrahydrofuran
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (76 : 24)	4500	200	10.4% "
	FeI ₂ -(SiO ₂ (79 : 21)	4500	200	6.2% "
Delta valero-lactone	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (78 : 22)	4600	200	28.8% tetrahydrofuran
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (76 : 24)	4600	200	13.6% "
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (79 : 17)	4680	200	6.8% "
Formic	NiI ₂ -(0.9% solu)	5500	200	6.8% carbonmonoxide
Methyl propionate (ethylene)	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	3600	230	21.5% methanol
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	3600	300	28.2% "
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	2650	260	24.0% "
Ethyl propionate (ethylene)	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	4200	230	36.0% ethanol
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	6000	230	45.0% "
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (85 : 15)	4400	230	43.6% "
Ethyl propionate (diethyl ether)	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	3500	230	28.9% ether
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	3300	230	23.2% "
	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	3400	230	22.7% "
Lactic acid	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	5100	230	44.36% acetaldehyde
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	5100	230	18.33% "
	Nickel acetate on silica gel, Ni : SiO ₂ (50 : 50)	5100	230	32.36% "
Methyl Lactate	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	1700	210	20.73% "
	Ni-acetate on silica gel (Ni : SiO ₂ =50 : 50)	1700	210	12.94% "
	Cu ₂ I ₂ +MnI ₂ on silica gel	1700	210	11.37% "
Ethyl Lactate	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	1800	230	13.84% "
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	1800	230	12.38% "
	Cobalt naphthenate on silica gel	1800	230	10.94% "
	Cu ₂ I ₂ +MnI ₂ on silica gel	1800	230	10.7% "
Benzoic Acid	No catalyst (thermal)	9100	360	80.9% on chlorobenzene
	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	6750	295	72.26% "
Methyl Benzoate	No catalyst (thermal)	4700	240	5.32%
	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	4600	240	22.10%
Acrylic acid	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (93 : 7)	510	205	8.5% on acetylene
	Nickel naphthenate	585	220	14.21% "
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	690	230	3.45 "
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	555	220	4.97 "
Methyl acrylate	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	525	170	47.3 "
	NiBr ₂ -SiO ₂ (80 : 20)	510	170	32.3 "
	Nickel naphthenate	750	280	28.3 "
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	795	255	5.3 "
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	810	255	9.1 "

Table III (contd.)

Acid of Ester	Catalyst	Pressure, p.s.i.	Optimum Temp. °C	% Conversion to acid or ester	
Ethyl acrylate	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	330	135	61.3	„
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	705	255	14.2	„
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	780	255	12.1	„
	Nickel naphthenate	510	255	47.21	„
n-propyl acrylate	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	367	140	58.8	„
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	600	200	32.1	„
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	780	240	18.6	„
	Nickel acetate on silica gel (Ni : SiO ₂ =50 : 50)	600	200	55.5	„
n-butyl acrylate	NiI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	395	160	80.0	„
	CoI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	500	200	43.3	„
	FeI ₂ -SiO ₂ (84 : 16)	760	240	24.09	„
	Nickel acetate on silica gel (Ni : SiO ₂ =50 : 50)	570	200	63.07	„

Effect of Temperature :—From the Figs. 1 (a, b, c) it is observed that the optimum temperatures for the syntheses of most of the compounds lie within very close range, 180 - 250°C.

Fig. 1a, 1b, 1c. Effect of reaction temperature on the conversion.

Product	Catalyst	Initial Pressure, p.s.i.	Time
AC Acetic acid	NiI ₂ /SiO ₂ , 84 : 16	2000	2
PR Propionic acid	"	2000	2
AD Adipic acid	NiI ₂ /SiO ₂ , 78 : 22	2500	3
DV Valerolactone	"	2500	3
GA Glycollic acid	NiI ₂ /SiO ₂ , 70 : 30	3000	5½
MG Methyl glycollate	"	3000	3
LA Lactic acid	NiI ₂ /SiO ₂ , 84 : 16	2600	3
FA Formic acid	0.9% of NiI ₂	3000	3
EP ₁ Ethyl propionate (from ethylene)	NiI ₂ /SiO ₂ , 84 : 16	2000	3
EP ₂ Ethyl propionate (from diethyl ether)	"	2000	3
AA Acrylic acid	"	210	3
MeA Methyl acrylate	"	210	4
EA Ethyl acrylate	"	210	2
PrA N propyl acrylate	"	210	2
BuA n butyl acrylate	"	210	2
ML Methyl lactate	"	1000	3
EL Ethyl lactate	"	800	3
BA Benzoic acid	"	2500	3
MB Methyl benzoate	"	2500	3

Effect of pressure :—The influence of carbon monoxide pressure on the yields of various compounds at the respective optimum temperatures is shown in the Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Effect of Reaction pressures on the conversion (symbols and catalysts as for Fig. 1)

	Temp. °C	Time, h.		Temp. °C	Time, h.
AC	180	2	FA	200	3
PR	230	2	EP ₁	230	3
AD	200	3	EP ₂	230	2
DV	200	3	ML	230	3
GA	200	5½	EL	230	3
MG	200	3	MB	240	3
LA	230	3			

Except for acrylic acid and its esters, where the optimum pressures are unusually low (30-45 atm.), the optimum pressures lie within the range, 300-400 atm.

Effect of residence period :—From the Figs. 3 (a, b) it is seen that the time required for the syntheses of most of the compounds at the respective optimum conditions of temperature and pressure are within 2 to 3 hr.

Fig 3a

Fig. 3a, 3b. Effect of residence time on the conversion (Symbols and catalysts as for Fig. 1)

Reaction	Temp. °C	Pressure p.s.i.
AC	180	3800
PR	230	4600
AD	200	4500
DV	200	5300
GA	200	5200
MG	200	5600
LA	230	5000
FA	200	5500
EP ₁	230	4200
EP ₂	230	3400
MeL	210	1700
EL	230	1750
BA	295	6600
MB	240	4600
AA	205	210*
MA	170	210*
EA	135	210*
PrA	140	210*
BuA	160	210*

*Initial Pressures

Fig 3b

Effect of catalyst composition :—From Fig. 4 it is clear that a catalyst composition of 50 : 50 (Ni/SiO₂) is best for the syntheses of most of the compounds studied.

Fig. 4 Effect of catalyst concentration on the conversion (Symbols and catalysts as in Fig. 1).

	Reaction		
	Temp. °C	Pressure, p.s.i.	Time, h
AC	210	4000	2
PR	230	4600	2
AD	300	4500	3
GA	215	5500	5½
LA	230	6000	3
EP ₁	230	4400	3
EP ₂	230	3600	2
EA	135	500	2

(Catalyst composition calculated as actual metal in halide present)

Life of the catalysts and the reactivation of "spent catalysts" :

In any catalytic work it is essential to know the life of the catalyst in use, that is, how long a catalyst sample can be used without any appreciable loss in its activity. Investigations in this aspect have thrown much light on the role of catalysts and mechanisms of the reactions.

TABLE IV

Life of the catalysts and methods of catalyst reactivation
Catalyst : nickel iodide-silica gel (Ni : SiO₂ : : 50 : 50)

	Process yields of the products, %			
	Fresh	Once used	Twice used	Twice used and water
Acetic acid from methanol	37.1	14.8	8.8	37.7
Propionic acid from ethanol	30.2	14.6	8.0	30.6
Ethyl propionate from ethylene	24.39	17.10	15.10	23.33
Methyl propionate from ethylene	19.96	9.50	—	18.29
Ethyl propionate from ether	22.73	17.66	7.1	19.76
Adipic acid from tetra hydrofuran	23.0	22.2	21.5	—
Ethyl acrylate from acetylene	61.34	10.38	9.88	22.82

Results in the Table IV clearly show that, in reactions, where water is one of the reactants, the catalysts suffer no appreciable loss in activity during use, but in other reactions, once used, twice used, or thrice used catalysts have much less activity than the original fresh catalysts. In the latter case, addition of small amounts of water is sufficient to restore the activity of the 'spent catalysts'. This definitely suggests that the presence of some water is essential for proper functioning of halide catalysts.

Role of the catalysts and probable mechanism of the reactions :

The outstanding observations, which have been made in the study of the above reactions, are :

- (1) Reduced metals and metal carbonyls are ineffective as catalysts.
- (2) Water is essential for these reactions.
- (3) Silica gel is the best catalyst support.

Based on the experimental results reported in various tables and graphs and the observations made as above the following three mechanisms may be suggested :

- (I) Mechanism based on the intermediate formation of metal carbonyls ;
- (II) Mechanism based on the intermediate formation of metal carbonyl halides of the type MX_2 , CO where M=Fe, Co or Ni, X=Cl, Br or I ;
- (III) Mechanism based on the intermediate formation of carbonium ions.

I. Mechanism based on the intermediate formation of metal carbonyl.

As all the three metals, iron, cobalt and nickel, are known to form carbonyls very easily, a reaction mechanism based on the intermediate formation of metal carbonyls, may be postulated for the reactions, a view held by a number of early workers also. According to Reppe,²⁷ the nickel iodide catalyst reacts with carbon monoxide as follows :

and the carbonyl then reacts with the other components to give the desired products.

If the formation of a metal carbonyl is the only prerequisite for the carbonylation reactions, the metal carbonyls themselves or even the reduced metals, which may form carbonyls very easily under the experimental conditions, should be very good catalysts. Table V shows the results obtained with cobalt carbonyl catalyst in the

TABLE V

Activity cobalt carbonyl catalyst in the synthesis of ethyl propionate

Amount of catalyst=2 g. Synthesis from ethylene+carbon monoxide+ethanol			Residence period=2 h. Synthesis from diethyl ether and carbon monoxide		
Temp., °C	Initial pressure, p.s.i.	Process Yield, %	Temp., °C	Initial pressure, p.s.i.	Process Yield, %
150	900	0.42	150	900	0.72
180	900	0.57	180	900	0.92
230	900	0.52	230	900	0.47
250	900	0.38	250	900	0.32
180	650	0.50	180	650	0.82
180	1100	0.47	180	1100	0.81
180	2000	0.46	180	2000	0.72
180*	900	0.56	180*	900	0.94

* Dicobalt octacarbonyl catalyst (2g.) mixed with elemental iodine (0.42 g.)

TABLE VI

*Activity of reduced metals supported on silica gel as
catalysts (metal/SiO₂ ratio 50 : 50)*

Synthesis	Temp., °C	Max. pressure, p.s.i.	Process conversion, %					
			Reduced Ni	Reduced Co	Reduced Fe	Nil ₂	Col ₂	Fel ₂
Acetic acid from methanol	210	4200	—	1.7	1.5	40.0	18.8	8.1
Propionic acid from ethanol	210	4200	1.8	2.1	1.9	37.3	22.3	8.1
Glycollic acid from formaldehyde	200	5500	0.7	0.8	0.7	29.0	23.8	16.8
Methyl glycollate from formaldehyde and methanol	200	5500	0	0	0.2	20.0	20.1	12.2
Ethyl glycollate from formaldehyde and ethanol	200	5500	0	0	0	24.0	20.5	11.8
Ethyl propionate from ethylene	230	4200	—	4.5	—	24.4	25.1	25.1
Acrylic acid from acetylene	200	450	0.62	0.24	—	6.82	4.7	6.12
Ethyl acrylate from acetylene	135	450	1.6	0.81	—	61.34	15.2	14.6

synthesis of ester from ethylene or from ether, and Table VI shows the activity of the reduced metals in the carbonylation reactions. From these tables it is evident that neither the carbonyl nor the reduced metal has any appreciable catalytic activity. Hence, it is clear this theory is not tenable.

(II) *Mechanism based on the intermediate formation of metal carbonyl halides.*

It has been reported by Hieber²⁸ that metal carbonyl halides of iron and cobalt are formed when their halides are allowed to react with carbon monoxide under pressure. According to Hieber, $\text{Co}(\text{Co})\text{I}_2$ is formed from CoI_2 and Co at 280 atm. and 100°C . Similar observation was made by Schulten and co-workers,²⁹ who isolated the compound as a dark brown crystalline substance having a very high dissociation pressure of carbon monoxide even at room temperatures. These authors, however, could not isolate similar complexes from nickel halides and carbon monoxide. It is very probable that nickel carbonyl halides are formed as very unstable intermediate complexes. From the electronic configuration of nickel, cobalt and iron, it appears that the stability of the various complexes will be in the order $\text{Fe} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni}$. Under the experimental conditions, it may be assumed, therefore, that the formation of a complex of the type $\text{M}(\text{CO})\text{X}_2$ occurs, ($\text{M} = \text{Fe}, \text{Co}$ or Ni and $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ or I). The complex thus formed may enter into reaction (2) for synthesis of acetic acid, for example, from methanol and CO and a molecule of metal halide or may react with more carbon monoxide as shown by reaction (3)

Reactions (2) and (3) are competitive and it is obvious that a higher partial pressure of carbon monoxide will diminish the yield of the product by destroying the active catalyst (reaction 3) and, similarly, a higher partial pressure of the reactant will favour the formation of more of the desired product.

The order of the activities of the various halides in the carbonylation reactions may be explained on the following assumptions: (i) of the various halides, iodides the least stable and hence form carbonyls most easily, and (ii) of the various halide complexes, nickel carbonyl iodide is the least stable and, therefore, is the most reactive for undergoing reactions as postulated above.

If the synthesis reactions actually proceed according to the scheme shown above, it may be expected that a lower carbon monoxide pressure with a higher partial pressure of the other reactant will be beneficial for the reactions. Experimental results shown in Fig. 2 & Fig. 5, showing the effect of carbon monoxide pressure and the mole ratio of the reactants respectively, are not in agreement with this. Besides, the essential need for the presence of moisture in the catalysts is not understandable if this mechanism is actually operative. Hence, it may be concluded that this mechanism alone cannot satisfactorily explain the course of the reaction.

28. W. Hieber, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1937, 43, 390.

29. W. Hieber, H. Schulten and R. Martin, *Z. anorg. u. allgem. chem.*, 1939, 240, 261; 1939, 243, 145.

Fig 5

Fig. 5. Effect of mole ratio of carbon monoxide to other reactant. (Catalyst : nickel iodide—silica 50 : 50 ; symbols as Fig. 1).

	Temp. °C	Reaction Pressure, p.s.i.
AC	210	4200
PR	210	4200
EP ₁	230	4500
EP ₂	230	4200
EA	135	500
LA	230	6000

(III) Mechanism based on the intermediate formation of carbonium ion :

As all the catalysts effective in the carbonylation reactions are acidic in nature, a reaction mechanism based on the intermediate formation of carbonium ion may be suggested. A proton, an ancillary step in the formation of carbonium ion, may be supplied by the acidic silica gel support or by hydrolysis of the metal halide. It has been found that silica gel retains a certain percentage of moisture even if it is calcined at 600-800°C for a considerable period.³⁰ The residual water is bound to silica giving rise to a structure

30. W. Stober, *Kolloidzshr*, 1956, 145, 17.

and may supply a proton. It has been found, however, that non-acidic supports such as kieselguhr, pumice, etc., though inferior to silica gel, are quite satisfactory for the halide catalysts. Table VII shows the comparative activities of silica gel, kieselguhr, kaolin and pumice as supports for nickel iodide catalysts. The effectiveness of the non-acid supports indicates that the hydrolysis reaction in all probability occurs. The spent catalysts of the reaction showed the presence of some oxides or hydroxides of the metals. Hence, the following reaction may take place :

The hydrohalo-acid may also be formed by reaction (1).

TABLE VII

Comparative activity of the various supports
Catalyst : nickel iodide-silica gel (Ni : support = 50 : 50)

Acid or ester	Temp., °C	Pressure, p. s. i.	% conversion to acid or ester			
			Silica gel	Kiesel -guhr	Kaolin	Pumice
Acetic acid from methanol	210	4200	37.0	24.0	14.5	21.2
Glycollic acid from formaldehyde	200	5500	29.0	19.2	14.0	17.5
Methyl glycollate from formaldehyde	200	5500	20.0	14.8	—	—
Ethyl glycollate from formaldehyde	200	5500	24.0	12.1	—	—
Adipic acid from tetrahydrofuran	200	4500	19.7	11.3	6.5	8.5
Ethyl propionate from ethylene	230	4200	24.4	17.9	19.3	17.8

The water required for these reactions may come from the catalyst itself (all the halide catalysts used in the investigations contained about 40% water). This explains why the presence of a small amount of water is essential for the proper functioning of the catalysts and also why the spent catalysts may be regenerated by addition of some water.

The effect of water on the activity of the catalyst was quantitatively assessed by carrying out a few experiments with cobalt iodide/silica gel catalyst containing precisely known amounts of water. This catalyst was prepared by crystallising cobalt iodide, $CoI_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, by vacuum evaporation of the solution and thoroughly mixing a known amount of the crystals with silica gel dehydrated by heating at different temperatures. The results obtained are recorded in Table VIII. This Table clearly shows that the activity of the catalyst is largely dependent on the water content.

TABLE VIII

Effect of variation of water in the catalyst in the synthesis of ethyl propionate from ethylene, carbon monoxide and ethanol

Catalyst : cobalt iodide		- silica gel (Co/SiO ₂ 50 : 50)				
Temperature=230°C		Residence period=3 h				
Initial pressure=2000 p.s.i.		Amount of catalyst=5 g.				
Maximum pressure=4200 p.s.i.		Moles of ethanol=0.25				
Moles of carbon monoxide=0.53		Moles of ethylene=0.55				
% Water in the catalyst	40*	20	2	16.4	7.2	3.7
Ethylene converted to ethyl propionate, %	24.4	12.7	10.1	6.2	2.7	

*Ordinary catalyst

All the foregoing discussions point towards the fact that the formation of hydrohalo-acid by hydrolysis of the halides is highly probable.

Based on this mechanism, it is postulated that, hydriodic acid, for example, by interaction with the starting materials gives carbonium ions thus : from alcohols ROH, R⁺ ; from ethers ROR¹, R⁺ (+R¹OH) ; from ethylene, $\overset{+}{C}H_2 \cdot CH_2$; from acetylene, $\overset{+}{C}H : CH_2$; and from aldehydes RCH₂ · CHO, RCH₂ · $\overset{+}{C}H \cdot OH$. The carbonium ions thus formed may react with carbon monoxide.

Normal carbon monoxide molecule may be assumed to resonate between the three forms

Although the very low dipole moment of carbon monoxide molecule led Pauling³¹ to suggest that forms (a) and (c) make approximately equal contributions, the molecular orbital treatment by other authors led them to conclude that form (c) should predominate. Form (c) of the carbon monoxide molecule may easily react with carbonium ions to give new carbonium ions.

Carbonium ions (5) may react, either with water to give carboxylic acids, or with alcohols to give esters, and in both cases a proton will be re-generated,

If the presence of a proton donor is the only prerequisite for the carbonylation reaction to take place as demanded by this theory, the hydrohalo-acids themselves

31. L. Pauling. 'Nature of the Chemical Bond', 2nd edn., 1940, p. 135 (New York : Cornell Univ. Press).

should have good catalytic activity. Table IX shows the activity of hydrogen iodide and of hydrogen bromide in the synthesis of ethyl propionate from ethylene and from ether.

TABLE IX

Activity of hydriodic and hydrobromic acids as catalysts in the synthesis of ethyl propionate

(temperature, 230° ; residence time, 2 h ; wt. of catalyst 3 g.)

Starting material	% Conversion to ester	
	HBr	HI
Ethylyne*	11.7	19.4
Ether**	5.21	7.57

* 4200 p. s. i.

** 4500 p. s. i.

From Table IX it may be seen that the hydrohalo-acids have considerable catalytic activities. The higher activity of the metal halides over the corresponding hydrohalo-acids may be explained by assuming that an unstable metal carbonyl halide complex as postulated in Mechanism II above is formed as an intermediate product. This unstable complex will split off active carbon monoxide continuously which will enter into the reaction more readily and actively.

The order of activity of the halides, viz., iodide > bromide > chloride, may be explained by the fact that iodides will most readily hydrolyse and also will form the complex most readily. It is important to note that a fraction of the carbonium ions formed by the attack of protons may react with the halogen radical of the hydrohalo-acids to give alkyl halides.

Small quantities of alkyl halides could actually be detected in the product in some cases. The tendency of alkyl halide formation will be minimum with iodide and the stability of the halides is in the order ; $RCl > RBr > RI$. This also explains the higher activity of the iodides. The alkyl halides thus formed may of course give rise again to the same product by an identical course of reaction as the parent compounds. Here the reactivity of the halides will be in order ; $RI > RBr > RCl$.

The reason for the superior activity of nickel halides over cobalt and iron halides has already been explained under Mechanism II.

The higher specific surface area of silica gel and its proton donor power explain its superiority to other catalyst supports used in the investigations.

Other miscellaneous reactions under pressure :—Some other reactions of industrial importance have also been carried out. The literature on these syntheses is industrially

meagre. Except for the papers published by the author and his co-workers³²⁻³⁸, only a few published papers are available.

- (i) Syntheses of esters from carboxylic acids and ethylene³².
- (ii) Synthesis of potassium salicylate from phenol, carbon dioxide and potassium carbonate³³.
- (iii) Synthesis of *p*-cresotic acid from *p*-cresol and carbon dioxide³⁴.
- (iv) Synthesis of diphenyl amine from aniline and hydrochloric acid³⁵.
- (v) Synthesis of 2-nitro diphenyl amine from aniline and *o*-chloronitro benzene³⁶.
- (vi) Synthesis of *p*-amino salicylic acid from *m*-amino phenol and carbon dioxide³⁷.
- (vii) Vinylation : Syntheses of vinyl ethers from acetylene and alcohols³⁸.

The optimum temperature, pressure, residence period, etc. with the best catalysts for the syntheses reactions have been included in Table X.

TABLE X

Esterification of Carboxylic acids	Temp., °C	Pressure, p.s.i.	Residence period, hrs.	Best Calalyst	Max. conversion
1. Ethyl acetate (C ₂ H ₄ + CH ₃ COOH →)	150	1100	3	12M H ₂ SO ₄	86.9 on input acid basis
2. Ethyl propionate (C ₂ H ₄ + C ₂ H ₅ COOH →)	185	1500	1	"	79.4 % on input propionic acid
3. Ethyl butyrate (C ₂ H ₄ + C ₃ H ₇ COOH →)	185	1900	3	"	61.5 % on input butyric acid
<i>Vinylation of acetylene</i>					
4. Ethyl vinyl ether (CH=CH + C ₂ H ₅ OH →)	185	240	3	Sodium metal of concn. 5% in alcohol	47.7 % on acetylene basis
5. Propyl vinyl ether (CH=CH + C ₃ H ₇ OH →)	200	450	3	5 gms of KOH	61.6% on acetylene basis
6. Butyl vinyl ether (CH=CH + C ₄ H ₉ OH →)	200	380	3	2 gms of KOH	50.7 % on acetylene basis.
<i>Miscellaneous reactions :</i>					
7. Potassium salicylate	175	120	6.0	Anhydrous K ₂ CO ₃ in phenol (1 : 3 wt. ratio)	90.3% phenol.
8. <i>p</i> -Amino salicylic acid	175	44	1.5	Sodium carbonate (1.39 M soln in water)	67.5% of <i>m</i> -amino phenol.
9. <i>p</i> -Cresotic Acid	210	95.2	3.0	Sodium carbonate (6.29 M soln. in water)	45.33% of <i>p</i> -cresol.
10. Diphenyl amine from aniline and hydrochloric acid	200	113.3	2	—	25% of aniline.
11. Diphenyl amine from aniline and aniline hydrochloride	350-400	113.3	2	—	18.07% aniline
12. 2-Nitrodiphenyl amine	180	81.6	2	—	48.6% of aniline

32. S. K. Bhattacharyya, and C. R. Lahiri, *J. Appl. Chem* (London), 1963, 13 544.

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The kinetics and mechanism of liquid phase reactions at high pressures.

The effect of pressure on reaction rates in solution was studied for the first time, about 70 years ago. Though some of the earlier workers observed a profound influence of pressure on the velocity of reaction, the first theoretical interpretation of the effect of pressure was put forward by Gibson³⁹ and Fawcett^{39, 40} followed by Evans and Polanyi⁴¹. Stern and Eyring⁴² derived an expression for the homogeneous liquid phase reaction from the absolute reaction rate theory, as follows :

$$RT. \left(\frac{\partial \ln k.}{\partial P} \right)_T = - \Delta V^*$$

where ΔV^* is the volume of activation, change in the molar volume resulting from the transformation of the reactants into an activated complex ; k, reaction rate constant.

Newitt⁴³ and his collaborators were probably the first to start a systematic study on effect of pressure on the rate and activation parameters for liquid phase organic reactions.

The knowledge of volume of activation ΔV^* is very helpful in elucidating the mechanisms of reactions. It is only recently that much interest is shown towards the interpretation of ΔV^* and its relation to the structure of the activated complex. The significance of the volume of activation can be more easily understood at an elementary level than that of free energy, enthalpy or entropy of activation because ΔV^* is determined primarily by the nuclear positions of the constituent atoms of the activated complex while ΔH^* , ΔF^* , ΔS^* are governed also by inter atomic forces and vibrations.

Recently Whalley^{44, 45}, Haman, Weale, Gonikberg and many others have studied the kinetics of a number of liquid phase reactions under pressure in order to ascertain their mechanism from the knowledge of volume of activation ΔV^* , as a characteristic and distinct parameter which is dependent on the reaction mechanism but fairly independent of the specific nature of the compounds involved. This method has been found to be particularly useful for suggesting the mechanism of acid and base catalysed reactions about which sometimes the standard methods of mechanistic study fail to furnish any definite conclusion. Whalley suggested that for any reaction, catalysed by hydrogen ions, in which the substrate accepts the proton on the oxygen atom, ΔV^* will be positive, zero or slightly negative for an A-1 mechanism and negative by several $\text{Cm}^3 \text{mole}^{-1}$ for A-2 mechanism.

39. R. O. Gibson, E. W. Fawcett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 386, 396.

40. E. W. Fawcett and R. O. Gibson, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1935, A 150, 223.

41. M. G. Evans and M. Polanyi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 875.

42. A. E. Stern, H. Eyring, *Chem. Revs.*, 1941, 99, 509.

43. D. M. Newitt, R. P. Linstead, R. H. Sapiro and E. J. Boorman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 876, and later papers.

44. E. Whalley, R. J. Withey, J. E. Mcalduff, 'Physics and Chemistry of High Pressure', *Ind. Chem. Soc. London*, 1962.

45. E. Whalley, *Trans. Faraday Soc.* 1959, 55, 798 and later papers.

In the high pressure laboratory at Kharagpur, Bhattacharyya and Purohit⁴⁶ have recently made important investigations on the application of the volume of activation and other activation parameters for studying the mechanism of the following reversible acid-catalysed reactions at high pressures :

- (i) the hydration of crotonic acid to β -hydroxybutyric acid and its reverse reaction.
- (ii) The hydration of crotonaldehyde to β -hydroxybutyraldehyde and its reverse reaction.
- (iii) The hydrolysis of γ -butyrolactone to γ -hydroxybutyric acid and its reverse reaction.

The activation parameters, E , ΔS^* , ΔV^* and the order of the reactions for each of the above cases have been determined (Tables XI & XII). The activation parameters have been used for finding the mechanism of the above reactions in presence of perchloric acid at a pressure ranging upto about 2500 atm.

TABLE XI

Effect of pressure on the rate and equilibrium constants

Reaction	Temp. °C,	Initial concentration molarity	Concentration of perchloric acid, normality	Pressure, kg./cm. ²	$k_1 \times 10^5$ sec. ⁻¹	$k_{-1} \times 10^5$ sec. ⁻¹	K	$k'_1 \times 10^5$ i. mol. ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹	$k'_{-1} \times 10^5$ i. mol. ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹
Hydration of crotonaldehyde	30.0	0.055	1.80	1*	1.464	1.543	0.9488	0.8134	0.1571
"	"	"	"	2,060	6.753	2.203	3.066	3.755	1.227
Hydration of crotonic acid	83.0	0.025	2.625	1*	28.21	5.417	5.210	10.74	2.16
"	"	"	"	1,406	66.01	11.65	5.666	25.15	4.438
Hydrolysis of γ -butyrolactone	35.0	2.947	0.10	1*	5.531	18.089	0.3058	55.31	180.89
"	"	"	"	2,110	12.00	24.830	0.4833	120.00	248.30

TABLE XII

Activation parameters at different pressures

Reaction	Pressure, kg./cm. ²	Energy of activation, kcal/mole		Entropy of activation, cal./deg. mole		Frequency factor, L/mole. sec.		Volume of activation, cm. ³ /mole		ΔV^\ddagger cm. ³ /mole
		E_1	E_{-1}	ΔS_1	ΔS_{-1}	$\log A_1$	$\log A_{-1}$	ΔV^*_{-1}	ΔV^*_{-1}	
Hydration of crotonaldehyde	1*	18.39	22.23	-23.27	-11.44	8.17		-19.8 (35°C)	-5.8 (35°C)	-12.3 (30°C)
	703	14.52	22.24	-34.75	-10.20			-19.6 (30°C)	-5.7(30°C)	
	2,060	14.02	23.30	-34.07	-6.08			—	—	—

46. S. K, Bhattachayya and G. B. Purohit, Ph. D. thesis submitted by G. B. Purohit at I.I.T., Kharagpur, 1966.

Table XII (contd.)

	Pressure, kg/cm. ²	Energy of activation, kcal/mole		Entropy of activation, cal./deg. mole		Frequency factor, L/mole sec.		Volume of activation, cm. ³ /mole		ΔV° cm. ³ /mole
				*	*	log A ₁ ,	Log A ₋₁			
Hydration of crotonic acid	1*	18.56	17.93	-35.82	-39.07	5.45		-18.09 (88.4°C)	-14.61 (88.4°C)	-3.47 (88.4°C)
								-17.89 (83°C)	-15.00 (83°C)	
	703	16.70	17.77	-38.39	-39.19	4.76		—	—	—
	1,406	16.03	16.15	-39.25	-42.70	4.24		—	+	—
Hydrolysis of γ butyrolactone	1*	16.68	16.44	-19.32	-17.74	8.58	8.93	-9.83 (35°C)	-3.5 (35°C)	-5.55 (38°C)
	703	17.22	16.87	-16.94	-16.17	9.10	9.28	—	—	—
	2,110	15.22	14.31	-22.58	-24.18	7.88	5.51	—	—	—

* At 1 atmosphere

The hydrations of crotonaldehyde and crotonic acid have similar characteristics. In either case the reaction follows the first order kinetics with respect to both hydrogen ion concentration and the reactant concentration. According to the classical Zucker-Hammett hypothesis it has been found that both the reactions proceed through transition states which contain at least one molecule of water. The kinetic data have been analysed in the light of Bunnett's concept of acid-catalysis. It has hence been concluded that the reactions follow an A-2 mechanism which purports that the solvent molecules take part in the rate controlling step. The highly negative values of entropy and volume of activations (Table XII) indicate the partial immobilisation of the solvent molecules in the transition states and thereby suggest an A-2 mechanism for the reactions. The total volume changes (ΔV°) accompanying the hydration of crotonaldehyde and crotonic acid have also been calculated from the pressure dependence of the respective equilibrium constants, as follows :

$$\left(\frac{\partial \ln K}{\partial P}\right)_T = -\frac{\Delta V^\circ}{RT} \text{ where } K = \text{equilibrium constant.}$$

The various kinetic parameters like rate constant, frequency factor, etc. of these two reactions have been critically examined in order to indicate the possible bearing of the functional group on the kinetics and mechanism of the acid-catalysed hydration.

An extensive study on the kinetics of reversible hydrolysis of γ -butyrolactone to γ -hydroxybutyric acid as well as its back reaction at high pressure has been made using perchloric acid as the catalyst. Both hydrolysis and lactonization provide interesting study since these involve the breaking and closure of the ring respectively. As before, the kinetic order of these reactions was first established. The proportionality of the rate of reaction with the concentration of hydrogen ion in either direction indicated A-2 mechanism. Further experimental evidence for this contention was obtained from the negative values of entropy and volume of activation. In the

present context it is worth mentioning, judging from the negative values of entropy of activation, that the lactonization of γ -hydroxybutyric acid seems to follow an A-2 mechanism which is in conflict with the mechanism suggested by the earlier workers on the basis of the Hammett's theory.

Mechanism of the acid-catalysed reactions at high pressures :—I shall now discuss briefly the mechanism of one of the above reactions, as for example, the hydration of crotonaldehyde, a conjugated double bond system ($-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{O}$) which may exhibit the characteristic of Lewis acid or base due to the presence of multiple bond like $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$. This behaviour is marked for the polar bond like $>\text{C}=\text{O}$, because the π electron density is displaced from the symmetrical distribution towards the more electronegative oxygen atom. This exposes the nucleus of the carbon atom more to attack by a nucleophilic agent. It is generally considered that the transfer of a proton to or from the oxygen atom takes place instantaneously due to the highly basic character of the oxygen atom. In a strongly acidic medium the protonation of crotonaldehyde may take place as

The charge on the functional carbon atom will be transferred to the β carbon atom due to resonance.

This protonated substrate with a positive charge on the β carbon atom may react with a molecule of water as

The highly negative value of the volume and the entropy of activation as observed in the present investigation, in addition to the variation of rate with hydrogen ion concentration, suggest that the transition state consists of at least one molecule of water.

On the basis of above conclusion the following mechanism for the hydration may be suggested.

The pre-equilibrium proton transfer step (1) will give carbonium ion. This carbonium ion being allylic is stabilised by the resonance as

This carbonium ion is further stabilised by hyperconjugation. Among the structures II and III, the latter is more contributing. Taking III, the nucleophilic attack of water on the protonated substrate (carbonium ion III) will be

The structures IV and V represent the transition state. The transition state then reacts with another molecule of water to give the product and the hydronium ion

